

Checklist for reporting cell counting studies

This checklist gives a guide to researchers reporting the results of a cell counting study, to ensure that all the sufficient and necessary details for interpretation and re-use of the data are provided. The checklist is divided into three parts: (1) Reporting methodological details in journal articles; (2) Providing data in a machine-readable format; and (3) Sharing data in accordance with the FAIR principles.

(1) Reporting methodological details in journal articles

Include information about animal experiments adhere to the ARRIVE guidelines. *Note: A detailed checklist to ensure adherence to these guidelines can be found online¹.*

Include RRIDs for primary and secondary antibodies used in the study. *Note: search for the catalogue number or name of the antibody in the Scicrunch repository². If the antibody is not in the repository, consider registering it in the system or as a minimum, report the company and catalogue number in your paper.*

Include information about the length of primary and secondary antibodies

If 3,3-diaminobenzidine (DAB)-staining was used, include the incubation time

Include an unambiguous definition of the anatomical region of interest. *The reporting of anatomical regions should include the following³:*

Name of the region

Reference atlas used, with version. If no reference atlas was used, state so, and define the criteria used to recognize the region of interest.

Whether the whole region was sampled. If only a subset (e.g. the anterior part) was sampled, state so, and indicate as unambiguously as possible the range covered.

A figure illustrating the region of interest, where the region can be seen in relation to major anatomical landmarks

Include information about the hardware used to image data:

Provide information on what type, brand and version of microscope was used

State what objective size was used for analysis and / or imaging

In case images were acquired, state the format, compression type, and pixel size of the resulting images

Include counting method information:

Describe the sampling scheme (how many sections were sampled and what was the interval between them). If a biased sampling scheme was used (e.g. counting only in two sections from the middle of a region), explain why and detail how it was ensured that the same area was sampled across animals.

Describe the software used for counting and provide RRIDs for these

¹ <https://arriveguidelines.org/resources/author-checklists>

² <https://scicrunch.org/resources/data/source/nif-0000-07730-1/search>

³ <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fnana.2018.00082/full>

- Describe the criteria used for recognizing a cell. Preferably, include example images of what was considered a cell and what was not.
- Provide a statement on whether numbers provided in the paper are total number estimates or densities
- For density estimates, provide the unit (e.g. mm³)
- For total number estimates, provide a statement on whether they are uni- or bilateral
- For stereological studies, provide the height sub-fraction, area sub-fraction, number of counted sections, fields, and objects, as well as the coefficient of error
- For segmentation-based studies, describe how the quality of the results were assessed

(2) Providing data in a machine-readable format

Ensure all descriptive data from the study are available in tabular format. If there are too many numbers to be provided in a single page, or if there are limitations on the number of figures / tables in the journal, provide them as a supplementary file. If the journal does not allow supplementary files, such tabular data can be uploaded to a repository, e.g. Figshare or Zenodo, and cited in the paper.

Ensure all non-aggregated data from the study (i.e. data per specimen) are available in tabular format. Provide the non-aggregated data from your study as a supplementary file. If there are groups in your study, include columns to specify the group allocations of each subject. If the journal does not allow supplementary files, such tabular data can be uploaded to a repository, e.g. Figshare or Zenodo, and cited in the paper.

(3) Share data in accordance with the FAIR principles

Share the non-aggregated data from the study in a domain-specific repository. Share the non-aggregated data from your study through a repository that allows tagging with domain-specific metadata, for example the EBRAINS Knowledge Graph⁴.

For segmentation-based studies, also share:

- Segmented images or images showing the localization of counted objects
- Spatial metadata defining the registration of data to a reference atlas
- The raw image data used for analysis
- The coordinates defining the positions of each counted object in the reference atlas

Note: these points are meant to provide a guideline for the type of files that should be provided; the exact format and content might differ between studies depending on the software used to generate data.

Ensure that all shared files are provided in formats that can be used with open-source software.

Share any code that was used in the acquisition or analysis of the data.

⁴ <https://www.ebrains.eu/data/share-data/>